

Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on clinical competencies in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses at selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT: -

INTRODUCTION: This study investigates the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Program related to emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia on the level of clinical competencies among staff nurses.

METHOD: - Used quantitative research approach. Pre-experimental one-group pretest post-test research design was used. 60 samples was selected using a non- probability convenient sampling technique. The accessible population consisted of staff nurses who have experience of less than 2 years. As a intervention STP implemented, clinical competencies of the staff nurses improved.

RESULT: -

Findings related to clinical competencies before implementation of STP:

In the pretest, 95% of the staff nurses had poor knowledge, 5% had average knowledge. 98.3% need improvement, 1.7% were fairly competent.

Findings related to clinical competencies:

In the pretest, 95% of the staff nurses had poor knowledge, 5% had average knowledge. In the post-test, all of them had good knowledge. In the pretest, 98.3% of the staff nurses needed improvement, 1.7% were fairly competent. In the post-test, 18.3% were fairly competent, 81.7% were competent.

Findings related to Paired t-test on knowledge:

The average knowledge score of pretest was 3.6 which increased to 19.6 in the post-test. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Findings related to Paired t-test on practices:

The average practice score in the pretest was 2.6 which increased to 14.8 in the post-test. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected.

CONCLUSION: -

After Structured Teaching Programme clinical competencies of staff nurses are improved.

KEYWORDS: - Structured Teaching Programme, Clinical Competencies, Emergency management, Supraventricular Tachycardia, Staff Nurses.

INTRODUCTION:

Supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) is an umbrella term for fast heart rhythms arising from the upper part of the heart. Between 60 to 100 beats per minute is the typical resting heart rate. Tachycardia is a resting heart rate of more than 100 beats per minute. During SVT, the heart rate is about 150 to 220 beats per minute. Supraventricular tachycardia cases are increasing worldwide. Supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) is relatively common in adult Americans, with 89,000 newly diagnosed cases each year and a prevalence of 5,70,000 persons. Supraventricular tachycardia accounts for approximately 50,000 emergency department visits each year. The vagus nerve supplies parasympathetic motor fibers to the myocardium. Aortic baroreceptors found in the carotid bodies and the walls of the aortic arch are stimulated by a variety of methods in Valsalva Maneuvers. These receptors trigger an increase in vagal tone, which stimulates a bradycardia response at the level of the Atrioventricular node. This acts to prolong the refractoriness of the nodal tissue and disrupt the re- entry circuit.[1-4]

The goal of the Valsalva Maneuvers is to raise the tone of the vagal parasympathetic nervous system to identify and cure arrhythmias. In an attempt to stop episodes of steady supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) or distinguish SVT from ventricular tachycardias (VT), they are frequently used initially. Modified Valsalva Maneuver and Standard Valsalva Maneuver are two types of Valsalva Maneuver. Headstands, applied abdominal pressure, ocular pressure, and gag reflex stimulation are less prevalent techniques that are not covered here.[5]

The role of the critical care nurse (CCN) regarding the care of a patient with acute supraventricular tachycardia is vital. It includes monitoring the electrocardiogram (ECG) for rate and rhythm, assessing vital signs and reporting abnormal changes to the physician immediately, emotional support for the patient and family. Educate the patient about different Valsalva Maneuvers and how to perform them. Valsalva Maneuvers are performed safely and involve expiratory effort against a closed glottis in the sitting or supine position with the

increased intrathoracic pressure raised to 40 mmHg for 15-20 seconds after which the pressure is suddenly released and the breathing restored to normal pattern. This stimulates the baroreceptors in the aortic arch, resulting in increased parasympathetic tone that blocks the Atrioventricular Node. The Valsalva Maneuvers are effective in 20% to 50% of hemodynamically stable patients.[6]

METHODS:

Study Design: The investigator utilized a pre-experimental one-group pretest-post-test research design. [7]

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.[8]

Setting: Selected hospitals of the city

Sampling Technique: Non probability, convenient sampling technique.[9]

Population: Staff nurses who are working in hospitals and having experience less than 2 years.[10]

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention (Structured Teaching Programme). Post-intervention clinical competencies of the staff nurses were assessed. The data was collected from 23/12/2024 to 11/01/2025.

Data Collection

Demographic data collected from selected hospitals as per demographic characteristics: Age, Gender, Education, Source of information regarding Vagal Maneuvers, Experience in the hospital, Area of work. Knowledge of the staff nurses was assessed with a Self-structured knowledge questionnaire. The practice of the staff nurses was assessed with an Observational Checklist regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Method of data collection

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct research were obtained.
2. The purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was obtained from the participants.
4. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority.
5. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using a non-probability convenient sampling technique.
6. Informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better cooperation during the data collection.
7. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data were discussed.
8. The data gathering process began on 23/12/2024 to 11/01/2025.
9. Given a prepared tool containing.

Section A - Consent form

Section B - Tool for demographic variables.

Section C - Self-structured knowledge questionnaire on clinical competencies in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

10. Assessed knowledge and practices of staff nurses regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia through the knowledge questionnaire and observation checklist.
11. A Structured Teaching Programme was conducted on emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. (Modified Valsalva Maneuver)
12. Post-tests were collected after 7 days of intervention.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the pre-test and post-test scores.

Inferential statistics: Paired-t test was used to compare the pre-test and post-test of clinical competencies among the experimental group. Fisher's exact test is used to associate clinical competencies among nurses with their selected demographic variables.

Data Analysis:

Sample Size: The formula used for sample size is-

$$n = Z\alpha/2^2 * (SD^2) / MOE^2$$

Calculations,

$$n = Z\alpha/2^2 * (SD)^2 / (MOE)^2$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 (0.169^2) / (0.045)^2$$

$$n = 3.84 * 0.028 / 0.002$$

$$n = 0.107 / 0.002$$

$$n = 53.5$$

For this study sample size, n comes to be 53.5. So approximately 60 samples were taken.[11]

Sampling Criteria:[12]

Inclusion Criteria: Staff nurses who are

- Having clinical experience of less than 2 years
- in the induction period/probation period
- willing to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria: Those who have already undergone programs.

RESULTS:

Finding related to demographic characteristics of the participants.

Demographic characteristics of staff nurses:

Age: 20% of the staff nurses were in the group aged 22-32 years and 80% of them were in the group aged 32.1-42 years.

Gender: 46.7% of them were females and 53.3% of them were males.

Education: 80% of them were GNM, 5% of them were Basic B.Sc. In nursing, 10% of them had post-basic B. Sc. Nursing and 5% of them had M. Sc. Nursing.

Source of information regarding vagal maneuvers: 6.7% of them had information regarding vagal maneuvers from journals, 86.7% of them were uncertain about the source of information, 1.7% of them had information from their area of work and 5% of them had information regarding vagal maneuvers from the internet.

Experience in the hospital: 16.7% of them had 0-6 months of experience, 33.3% of them had 6.1 -12 months of experience, 21.7% of them had 12.1-18 months of experience and 28.3% of them had 18.1-24 months of experience.

Area of working: 31.7% of them were working in the emergency department, 43.3% of them were working in the intensive care unit, 18.3% of them were working inwards and 6.7% of them were working in some other area.

Findings related to clinical competencies in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia before implementation of the Structured Teaching Programme among staff nurses.

In the pretest, 95% of the staff nurses had poor knowledge and 5% of them had average knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. 98.3% of the staff nurses need improvement and 1.7% of them were fairly competent in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Findings related to the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on clinical competencies in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses

In the pretest, 95% of the staff nurses had poor knowledge and 5% of them had average knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. In the post-test, all of them had good knowledge regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. This indicates that there is a remarkable improvement in the knowledge among staff nurses regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia after a structured teaching program.

In the pretest, 98.3% of the staff nurses needed improvement and 1.7% of them were fairly competent regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. In the post-test, 18.3% of them were fairly competent and 81.7% of them were competent in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. This indicates that there is a remarkable improvement in the practices among staff nurses regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia after a structured teaching program.

Findings related to Paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses.

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses. The average knowledge score in the pretest was 3.6 which increased to 19.6 in the post-test. The t- value for this test was 87.5 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average knowledge score in the post-test was significantly higher than that in the pretest. The structured teaching program is significantly effective in improving the knowledge among

staff nurses regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Findings related to Paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on practices regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses.

The researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on practices regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses. The average practice score in the pretest was 2.6 which increased to 14.8 in the post-test. The t-value for this test was 57.6 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average practice score in the post-test was significantly higher than that in the pretest. The structured teaching program is significantly effective in improving the practices among staff nurses regarding the emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Since p-values corresponding to education, Source of information regarding vagal maneuvers, and area of working were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables education, Source of information regarding vagal maneuvers, and area of work were found to have a significant association with the knowledge among staff nurses regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have a significant association with the practices among staff nurses regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

DISCUSSION:

In the summary discussion brings the research report to a close. The research findings "made sense" in a well-written discussion section. The study is conducted in hospitals to improve the clinical competencies of staff nurses regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia by analyzing detailed demographic data encompassing age, gender, education,

source of information, experience, and Area of work. The initial assessment exposed a substantial deficiency in clinical competencies, with 95% of the staff nurses having poor knowledge and 5% of them having average knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. 98.3% of the staff nurses need improvement and 1.7% of them were fairly competent in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia.

This prompted the implementation of the Structured Teaching Programme. Post-test outcomes revealed significant progress, with 100% attaining good knowledge scores 18.3% of them were fairly competent and 81.7% of them were competent in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia. This improvement was strongly supported by statistical analysis, including the rejection of the null hypothesis through paired t-test analysis. The average knowledge score in the pretest was 3.6, which increased to 19.6 in the post-test. The t-value for this test was 87.5 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small. The average practice score in the pretest was 2.6, which increased to 14.8 in the post-test. The t-value for this test was 57.6 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small. So the study was effective.

1. Comparison with an E-Learning Study on SVT Management.

Similarity: Both studies aim to improve knowledge and skills in SVT management.

Difference: The referenced study uses a randomized controlled design and compares two teaching methods, whereas this study employs a single-group pretest-posttest design.

2. Comparison with a Study on Basic Life Support (BLS) Training

Similarity: Both studies target staff nurses and use a similar design to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programs.

Difference: The BLS study focuses on general emergency response, while this study is specific to SVT management.

3. Comparison with a Disaster Management Training Program

Similarity: Emphasis on structured training to improve emergency response competencies.

Difference: The disaster management study uses a more robust design and incorporates diverse teaching methods, whereas this study get benefit from integrating such strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.
- A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized.
- The study can be replicated in different settings.
- The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study.
- Other interventions rather than a Structure Teaching Programme can also be used in the study.

ABBREVIATIONS:

1. SVT: Supra-Ventricular Tachycardia
2. STP: Structured Teaching Programme
3. EM: Emergency
4. ICU: Intensive Care Unit
5. VM: Valsalva Maneuver

Table 1.1: Knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia before implementation of the Structured Teaching Programme among staff nurses n=60

Knowledge	Pretest	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor	57	95.0
Average	3	5.0
Good	0	0.0

Table 1.2: Practices regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia before implementation of the Structured Teaching Programme among staff nurses

n=60

Practices	Pretest	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Needs Improvement	59	98.3
Fairly competent	1	1.7
Competent	0	0.0

Table 2.1: Effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses n=60

Knowledge	Pretest		Post-test	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor	57	95.0	0	0.0
Average	3	5.0	0	0.0
Good	0	0.0	60	100.0

Table No 2.2: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses

n=60

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	3.6	1.4	87.5	59	0.000
Post-test	19.6	0.7			

Table 2.3: Effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on practices regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses

n=60

Practices	Pretest		Post-test	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Needs Improvement	59	98.3	0	0.0
Fairly competent	1	1.7	11	18.3
Competent	0	0.0	49	81.7

Table 2.4: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of the Structured Teaching Programme on practices regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses

n =60

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	2.6	1.7	57.6	59	0.000
Post-test	14.8	0.5			

Fig No 1: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to pretest knowledge in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses.

FIG NO 2: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to pretest practices in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses.

Fig No 3: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to knowledge regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses in pretest and post-test.

Fig No.4. Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to average knowledge score in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses in pretest and post-test.

Fig No 5: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to practice regarding emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses in pretest and post-test.

Fig. No 6: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to average practice score in emergency management of supraventricular tachycardia among staff nurses.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Wikipedia contributors. Supraventricular tachycardia [Internet]. Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. 2023. Available from:
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Supraventricular_tachycardia&oldid=1189829781
- [2] Al-Khatib, S. M., & Page, R. L. Acute treatment of patients with supraventricular tachycardia. *JAMA Cardiology*, 1(4), 483. (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2016.1483>
- [3] Murphy, S. D., & Torlutter, M. The use of vagal maneuvers in narrow complex tachyarrhythmias in primary care. *South African Family Practice*, 64(1). (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.4102/safp.v64i1.5413>
- [4] Supraventricular tachycardia. (2022, April 30). Mayo Clinic.
<https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/supraventricular-tachycardia/symptoms-causes/syc-20355243>
- [5] Ashraf, H., Fatima, T., Ashraf, I., & Majeed, S. Effectiveness of modified Valsalva Maneuvers by using wide bore syringe for emergency treatment of supraventricular tachycardias: Findings from Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences Quarterly*, 39(3), 693. (2023). <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.39.3.6725>
- [6] Valsalva Maneuvers with supraventricular tachycardia. (2019, July 12). Acls.com.
<https://acls.com/articles/vagal-maneuvers/>
- [7] Alam M. What is a research design? Definition, types, methods and examples [Internet]. IdeaScale. 2023 [cited 2025 Mar 30]. Available from:
<https://ideascale.com/blog/what-is-research-design/>

- [8] Solanki K. What is Research Approaches ? [Internet]. Top4u. Blogger; 2025 [cited 2025 Mar 30]. Available from: <https://www.toppers4u.com/2022/01/what-is-research-approaches-meaning-and.html>
- [9] Bisht R. What are sampling methods? Techniques, types, and examples [Internet]. Researcher.life. 2023 [cited 2024 Aug 30]. Available from: <https://researcher.life/blog/article/what-are-sampling-methods-techniques-types-and-examples/>
- [10] Simplilearn. Population vs sample: Definitions, differences, and examples [Internet]. Simplilearn.com. Simplilearn; 2021 [cited 2024 Aug 30]. Available from: <https://www.simplilearn.com/tutorials/machine-learning-tutorial/population-vs-sample>
- [11] What is sample size? [Internet]. Coursera. 2023 [cited 2025 Feb 26]. Available from: <https://www.coursera.org/articles/what-is-sample-size>
- [12] Wikipedia contributors. Inclusion and exclusion criteria [Internet]. Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. 2023. Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Inclusion_and_exclusion_criteria&oldid=1189002623